

PARAMETRIC FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF CRITICAL DELAMINATIONS IN COMPOSITE STIFFENED PANELS

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SUMMARY: The analysis of skin delaminations in composite stiffened panels was performed using an automated finite element modelling tool – COMposite Panel Defect Assessment Tool (Compdat). The postbuckling behaviour of the panel was captured and fracture mechanics was applied to predict the initiation of delamination growth. The driving force for delamination growth was the local and global buckling modes that develop under compression loading. The stresses developed at the delamination crack front can promote further splitting and separation following buckling. Parametric studies were conducted using Compdat to determine the critical parameters for skin delamination. Two stiffened panels with skin thicknesses of 2.25 mm and 3.50 mm were considered in the studies. It was found that the thinner panel was more flexible, and delamination growth was triggered in the pre-global buckling range of the panel. On the other hand, the thicker panel was subjected to more extensive damage growth in the post-global buckling range of the panel. The local buckling mode shape did not affect the corresponding global buckling mode shape of the panel in the far postbuckling range. The depth of the delamination was the critical factor in the propagation of delamination, while other influential parameters included shape, size and aspect ratio.

KEYWORDS: stiffened panel, finite element analysis, delamination, postbuckling, strain energy release rate

INTRODUCTION

Conservative design allowables have been widely adopted by the aircraft industry, primarily to accommodate strength degradation due to defects in composite structures. In the damage tolerant design of composite structures, there is more emphasis on inspections, on predictions of damage growth and on definition of critical damage conditions. With current advanced composite materials, normal service loads cause few problems, but accidental damage arising from manufacturing or in-service events can cause significant reductions in performance.

Impact damage or manufacturing defects can often result in delaminations in the composite laminate. Delamination can be considered to be failure of the bond between two plies, leading to separation. Loading conditions that promote separation of delamination can cause a loss of stiffness and strength that may constitute failure in high performance applications. Linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) is commonly used for the analysis of delamination growth in composite materials. Interlaminar tensile stresses give rise to Mode I fracture, and interlaminar shear stresses give rise to Mode II and Mode III fracture. In structures, however, delaminations are not normally loaded in pure Mode I or pure Mode II, but grow under a mixture of Mode I and Mode II loading. Therefore a mixed mode failure criterion is necessary to predict the delamination growth initiation. As thin shells are being considered, it is reasonable to disregard the Mode III loading [1].

Buckling usually commences locally in the delaminated region, often resulting in separation of two sub-laminates. At this point, the crack front is Mode I dominated. As the load increases, global

buckling takes place and changes the loading at the delamination front, leading to the increasing domination of Mode II. When the load approaches the ultimate load (UL) in the far postbuckling range, the global buckling mode may cause the delamination to close, in which case the crack front will be stressed mostly in Mode II. While the shape of delaminations resulting from impact damage is generally irregular, the major axis of the delamination is normally parallel to the fibre direction of the lower ply [2-4].

The ability to predict the effect of delaminations in composite structures is of great importance in improving design methods and reducing the magnitude of the conservative knockdown factors applied. Current certification requirements state that certain sized defects must be assumed to exist in the structure, and that no growth is permitted through the life of the airframe. The analysis approach used in this work can be used to accurately assess the effect of delaminations in complex, postbuckling, integrally stiffened structures. Such tools will enable the full potential of advanced composite materials to be exploited, leading to significant performance improvements.

BACKGROUND

An automated finite element (FE) analytical tool - COMposite Panel Defect Assessment Tool (Compdat), has been developed using Patran Command Language (PCL) to analyse skin delamination [5]. The tool is fully integrated into the MSC.Patran modelling environment for pre- and post-processing purposes. The FE analyses are performed in MSC.Nastran for the prediction of panel stiffness, characterisation of postbuckling behaviour and computation of element corner forces at the delamination crack front for the strain energy release rate (SERR) calculation. The analytical tool is coupled with a Fortran program to determine the onset of delamination growth using a mixed mode failure criterion. The modelling and analysis approach has been shown to compare well with experimental data for buckling and postbuckling behaviour [5,6].

Parametric studies were conducted with Compdat to establish the critical parameters for skin delamination in two-stringer, stiffened panels with skin thicknesses of 2.25 mm and 3.50 mm. The delamination parameters considered included the position in the laminate depth, aspect ratio, size and location in the panel. These parameters were investigated for both rectangular and elliptical shaped delaminations. For the elliptical delamination, the orientation of the ellipse was also investigated. The critical parameters were determined through prediction of the onset of delamination growth.

MODELLING AND ANALYSIS APPROACH

The panel, modelled using QUAD4 shell elements, was loaded in compression with clamped boundary conditions [5]. The analysis steps involved first a linear buckling analysis, followed by a geometric non-linear analysis, and finished with the SERR calculations.

Basic Modelling Approach

Two basic methods for representing the stiffened panel are implemented in Compdat: skin/stringer flange integral and differential models. The differential model, as described in Ref. 5, models the skin and stringer flange as two separate layers of shell elements. The offset between the two nodal planes is calculated based on the skin and stringer flange thicknesses. On the other hand, the integral model represents the skin and stringer flange as one layer of shell elements with the nodal plane of the elements placed at the mid-plane of the skin. In the stringer region, the sub-laminate is balanced with a dummy layer of near zero stiffness in order to offset the stringer by the flange thickness. Hence, the nodal plane maintains its position at the true mid-plane of the laminate, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Definition of the nodal plane in the integral FE modelling approach

Delamination Modelling Approach

The modelling of a damaged region was simplified to a two-dimensional problem, i.e. the crack was expected to extend along a single interface of the skin laminate and would not cross a ply, when the geometry would become three-dimensional. The local defect was expected to encounter stress concentrations and high strain gradients, so local mesh refinement was implemented. RSPLINE elements were used to connect the boundary nodes of this mesh with those on the surrounding coarser mesh. The RSPLINE element assumes a linear interpolation for displacement and rotations along the axis of the spline, a quadratic interpolation for rotations normal to the axis of the spline, and a cubic interpolation for displacements normal to the axis of the spline.

Additional layers of superimposed elements were required in the damaged region to represent the upper and lower sub-laminates. This enables the local buckling to be simulated, and was also an input requirement for the SERR calculations. It was very important to consider the nodal plane placement in the sub-laminates carefully, as it affects the bending and membrane coupling stiffnesses. The nodal planes of the intact and damaged regions were positioned in the mid-plane of the undamaged skin, as shown in Figure 2. While this approach did not exactly correspond to the real geometry of the delaminated region, it did produce good local deformation behaviour. Local bending due to in-plane strain was prevented through such a nodal plane arrangement, so unfavourable global deformation behaviour could result. This approach could cause problems for delaminations located towards the outer skin of the panel, but this could be overcome by application of imperfections corresponding to the local deformation state [7]. In the intact region surrounding the delamination, also represented by double-layer shell elements, dummy layers with near zero stiffness and appropriate thickness were introduced in order to balance the laminate with respect to its nodal plane, as shown in Figure 3. Contact elements were used in the delaminated area of the stiffened panel to prevent the sub-laminates from overlapping.

Figure 2: Nodal plane location (panel thickness view) of the delaminated region and crack front

Figure 3: Delamination modelling approach using zero stiffness layers showing nodal plane

For the elliptical shaped delamination, the geometry was defined using three points representing the centre, major radius and minor radius, from which an elliptical curve was created. The ellipse was then scaled to create an outer and inner curve in order to obtain regular element shapes around the delamination front. The rest of the region was meshed using a paver mesh, as shown in Figure 4. The entire ellipse and surrounding region has to remain within the skin bay of the stiffened panel. It is not yet possible to generate an elliptical delamination under the stringer flange with Compdat due to the complexities encountered in meshing the connected stringer web.

Figure 4: Elliptical delamination modelling in the skin bay using a paver mesh

PARAMETRIC STUDIES

The parametric studies on rectangular and elliptical delaminations were conducted on two-stringer, curved panels, as described in Table 1. These panels were representative of those found in commercial aircraft vertical tails. The delamination parameters considered were the position in the laminate, aspect ratio, size and location in the panel. The critical load was defined as the load level corresponding to the onset of crack growth, or corresponding to the maximum Failure Index (FI) if no growth was predicted up to the Ultimate Load (UL) of the panel. The majority of parametric studies were based on the 2.25 mm panel due to the lower buckling load. Limited parametric studies were conducted on the 3.50 mm panel to verify the findings for panels with thicker skins.

Table 1: Attributes of panels used in the parametric studies

Panel	Skin Thickness (mm)	Lay-up	Buckling Load (kN)	Ultimate Load (kN)
Thin	2.25	[45/-45/45/-45 ₂ /45/0/-45/45]	155	350
Thick	3.50	[45/-45/0 ₂ /45/-45/45/-45 ₂ /45/0 ₂ /-45/45]	300	450

Delamination Depth

An arbitrary rectangular delamination with the dimensions of 100 mm x 52.5 mm, located in the skin bay at the centre of the panel, was used for the delamination depth parametric study. The effect of the depth of this delamination was investigated ply-by-ply, and the results are presented in Figure 5. For the 2.25 mm panel, the most critical delamination depth was between the 6th & 7th plies (from the skin side), which divided the laminate with a ratio of 1:2. The delamination located towards the stringer side was more critical than those located towards the skin side, as the curved stiffened panel had the tendency to buckle towards the stringer side. The least critical delamination was between the 4th and 5th plies, where the laminate was divided into approximately two equal thickness sub-laminates.

Figure 5: Rectangular delamination depth parametric study results for the 2.25 mm panel

The effect of depth for an elliptical delamination was also investigated and the results are presented in Figure 6. It was found that the critical delamination depth was also between the 6th and 7th plies. An elliptical delamination in such a position is the most critical up to the limit load of the panel, but a delamination between 3rd and 4th plies achieved the highest FI in the far postbuckling range.

The most critical depth for the 3.50 mm panel was between the 11th and 12th plies up to the global buckling load. In the far postbuckling range, the most critical depth was between the 4th and 5th plies. The least critical delamination location was the mid-plane of the laminate. In the case of an elliptical delamination, most delamination depths had a similar critical load, except for those located in the mid-plane of the laminate, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 6: Elliptical delamination depth parametric study results for the 2.25 mm panel

Figure 7: Elliptical delamination depth parametric study results for the 3.50 mm panel

The global buckling load of the panels was not affected by such a delamination, regardless of its shape and position within the laminate. However, the local buckling loads varied greatly, depending on the thickness of the two sub-laminates.

Delamination Aspect Ratio

The effect of the aspect ratio of rectangular and elliptical delaminations between the 6th and 7th plies at the centre of the panel was investigated for the 2.25 mm panel. An aspect ratio of greater than 1 represented a delamination with its largest dimension in the panel's longitudinal direction. It was found that for a rectangular delamination, the critical case was an aspect ratio greater than or equal to 2.0, as shown in Figure 8, because the delamination had the tendency to propagate in the lateral direction. In general, an aspect ratio less than 2.0 was less critical, especially when the delamination extended into the stiffener bay. The critical case in the postbuckling range for an elliptical delamination was an aspect ratio less than or equal to 1.0, as shown in Figure 9. The effect of the aspect ratio was insignificant for loads below approximately 150 kN. In general, the global buckling load of the panel was not affected by delamination aspect ratio. On the other hand, the local buckling load for the square and circular delaminations was the lowest.

Figure 8: Effect of aspect ratio for the rectangular delamination

Figure 9: Effect of aspect ratio for the elliptical delamination

Delamination Size

The effect of net area of the rectangular and elliptical delaminations was investigated on the 2.25 mm panel. Again, the delamination was located between the 6th and 7th plies at the centre of the panel and an aspect ratio of two was used. A small rectangular delamination of less than 100 mm x 50 mm was non-critical, as shown in Figure 10, and the medium sized delaminations exhibited similar behaviour. The large delamination size of 210 mm x 105 mm was more critical. It should be noted that the next larger sized delamination, 270 mm x 135 mm, showed a reduced tendency for damage growth, since 22% of the damage region was under the stringer flange. However, the global buckling load of the panel with such a delamination was reduced by approximately 10%, as shown in Figure 11. For the elliptical delaminations, the critical load for all sizes was similar and is shown in Figure 12. The global buckling load was not affected, while the local buckling load reduced with increasing delamination size.

Figure 10: Effect of rectangular delamination size

Figure 11: Effect of rectangular delamination size on local and global buckling loads

Figure 12: Effect of elliptical delamination size

Delamination Location

The effect of the location of a 120 mm x 60 mm delamination between the 6th and 7th plies in the 2.25 mm panel was investigated in two stages: first, delamination in the skin bay region and second, delamination fully or partially under the stringer. It was found that the location of the delamination did not affect the critical failure load, except when located close to the boundary of the panel, in which case separation of the sub-laminates was restricted due to the clamped boundary condition. Also, the local and global buckling loads were not affected by the location of the rectangular delamination in the centre skin bay region. Figure 13 shows that local buckling initiated prior to global buckling, and then dissipated in the far postbuckling range. This was found to be the case regardless of the location of the delamination in the panel. The rectangular delamination in the stringer and skin bay region was also investigated. Different cases were considered: 25% to 100% of the delamination embedded under the stringer region. It was found that the critical failure load was over 210 kN for all cases.

Figure 13: Buckling mode progression for a delamination in the panel centre skin bay

Elliptical Delamination Orientation Angle

The orientation angle of a 100 mm x 50 mm elliptical delamination between the 6th and 7th plies was investigated. The orientation angle was defined in accordance with the principal axes of the stiffened panel, with 0° aligned with the lateral direction and 90° aligned with the longitudinal direction. The onset of crack growth for all orientation angles was the same in the pre-buckling range, as shown in Figure 14. However, the 90° elliptical delamination was most critical in the postbuckling range of the panel. The global buckling load was not affected by the orientation angle. However, the 90° elliptical delamination produced the highest local buckling load due to the smaller length in the longitudinal direction of the panel.

Figure 14 Effect of orientation of an elliptical delamination

DISCUSSION

Skin delaminations did not affect the far postbuckling mode shape of the panel, regardless of delamination parameters; local buckling of the delamination always dissipated beyond 80% UL. Delamination depth was found to be a more critical parameter than the size or location in the panel. The most critical delamination depth corresponded with a sub-laminate thickness at a ratio of 1:2,

with the thinner sub-laminate on the stringer side. Large delaminations led to stiffness reductions of the structure as the buckling load was significantly decreased. However, they were less likely to propagate due to the proximity of the stiffeners, and the buckling mode shape that resulted in crack closure. Delaminations located in the centre of the panel were slightly more critical than those located closer to a boundary. The skin thickness and laminate lay-up did not change the general trends in the critical parameters for skin delaminations. However, SERR values increased at a higher rate for thicker panels in the postbuckling range, as the thicker sub-laminates were able to store more energy and produce higher stresses at the crack front.

For the same aspect ratio and approximately the same area, rectangular delaminations were not as critical as elliptical or circular ones. Rectangular delaminations tended to propagate in the lateral direction of the panel, whereas elliptical ones tended to propagate in the longitudinal direction. The circular delaminations tended to propagate in a diagonal direction. The orientation angle of the elliptical delamination had little effect on the onset of failure, although it did change the predicted growth direction. As the angle increased, the delamination growth direction changed from the longitudinal to the lateral direction. For a rectangular delamination, an aspect ratio of 2.0 or higher was more critical, regardless of the other delamination parameters. However, an aspect ratio of 1.0 or lower was more critical for an elliptical delamination. This was because a rectangular delamination had the tendency to propagate longitudinally, whereas an elliptical one had the tendency to propagate laterally, with respect to their geometries.

CONCLUSION

Skin delaminations in stiffened panels under compressive loading produced a mixed mode loading condition at the crack front. These delaminated panels were analysed numerically with an automated analytical tool – Compdat, using a combined postbuckling and LEFM approach to determine the onset of growth. Compdat substantially reduced the modelling time and effort in the repetitive steps required for the parametric studies. The critical delamination parameters were determined through the predicted onset of damage growth. The parametric study results showed that the skin delamination damage mechanisms were complex and varied greatly depending on the size, shape, location and depth. The delamination depth of 33% and elliptical shape were found to be the most critical parameters influencing delamination growth. Other parameters, such as size, location, orientation angle and aspect ratio, played a lesser role in the damage propagation prediction. The parametric studies described in this paper have improved the understanding of the structural behaviour of delaminations in stiffened panels, which is useful for improved design of composite structures. Compdat can also be used for a rapid assessment of manufacturing and in-service defects.

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